

ACADEMIC PROCRASTINATION: ITS RELATIONSHIP TO THE ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE OF GRADE-12 SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS OF MINDANAO STATE UNIVERSITY-SULU, SOUTHERN PHILIPPINES

Shaima P. Juaini, Al-Mudzill D. Aming, Derhana L. Bahad, Al-Mukrien N. Harud, Mariam H. Ibnihasim, Fatima Shaira J. Balla, Shainalyn E. Adjuran

Mindanao State University-Sulu, Capitol Site, Jolo, Sulu, Philippines

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ABSTRACT

Studying the connections between academic procrastination and academic performance might shed light on how procrastination affects students' capacity to do assignments on time, use their time wisely, and succeed academically. To assist students overcome their procrastinating tendencies and improve their academic achievement, this research can help identify relevant treatments and support networks. This study aimed to examine the academic procrastination and academic performance of Grade-12 senior high school students of MSU-Sulu. In this context, the sample group of the study consisted of 120 respondents, 60 male and 60 female on both STEM and GAS strands, and was purportedly surveyed using the Procrastination Assessment Scale-Student (PASS) as an instrument. In addition, a survey questionnaire checklist was used as a data collection tool for the study. In analyzing the data, Frequency and Percentage, Mean, Independent sample T-test, and Pearson Correlation analysis were used. According to the analysis result, the level of academic procrastination is nearly always the independent variable. In regards to the level of academic performance, it was found that the student's level of academic performance is very satisfactory. Additionally, it was found that there is no significant gender difference in the student's academic procrastination level and that academic procrastination is associated with the student's academic performance with a very slight relationship. With the given findings, several recommendations are suggested such as organizing one's goal, eliminating distractions, and remembering the due dates to overcome academic procrastination.

Keywords: *Academic procrastination, academic performance, STEM, GAS, MSU-Sulu*

INTRODUCTION

Studying how students' academic performance is related to academic procrastination is beneficial for several reasons. Researchers can learn more about how postponing work or assignments impacts students' capacity to study and achieve academic success by investigating the link between academic procrastination and academic performance. Students who can recognize their procrastination tendencies and the consequences of those patterns can grow in self-awareness with the aid of procrastination studies. Neglecting to complete tasks on time can have detrimental repercussions on learning and performance, including failing grades and course dropouts (Aremu et al., 2011, Balkis, 2013). Many other academic problems are linked to procrastination, including lower exam scores, lower grades, needing to retake assignments, higher course failure rates, higher course withdrawal rates, longer study times, and a higher chance of dropping out (as opposed to graduating). Students frequently claim that procrastination takes up more than a third of their daily activities, usually in the form of sleeping, watching TV, or playing video games. This finding is linked to the problems that arise from procrastination's tendency to take up a large amount of time for the students.

Procrastination is called the "Mañana Habit" in Filipino, also called "Mamaya Na" habit. (Mejia, 2017) There has long been an issue with this type of behavior. And for that reason, this kind of occurrence spreads quickly throughout generations. The Spanish term *mañana* translates to "future" or "tomorrow" in English. One of the worst characteristics of certain Filipinos is their "Mañana Habit." It is a particular kind of bad behavior that makes them put off doing the current activity indefinitely.

Additionally, procrastination has a variety of consequences in Mindanao. Students' learning productivity is impacted, which results in poorer academic achievement. Furthermore, it impedes the peace process in the area, since foreign terrorists have integrated themselves into the long-running Moro Islamic insurgency, turning Mindanao into a front line in the fight against terror in the region. Furthermore, procrastination exacerbates low school attendance, which has a detrimental effect on pupils' academic achievement.

Moreover, Academic Procrastination is a behavior many individuals struggle with, and its relationship can be particularly impactful, especially on Grade 12 senior high school students at MSU-Sulu. As the final year of their high school journey, Grade 12 is a crucial period marked by academic challenges, college preparations, and career decisions. Understanding the consequences of procrastination on these students is essential in supporting their educational success and personal development.

Researching how academic procrastination is related to academic performance can help produce useful insights, and practical solutions, support students, enhance the learning environment, and promote long-term skill development. In the end, these advantages help to improve educational results and get pupils ready for success in the classroom and the workplace. Nevertheless, other research (Seo, 2011; Solomon and Rothblum, 1984) has not found any correlation between academic procrastination and academic performance, and some studies (Brinthaup and Shin, 2001; Schraw et. al,

2007) have even found that academic procrastination improves academic achievement. Research has indicated that pupils with higher ability levels tend to put off tasks longer than those with lower ability levels (Ferrari, 1991). Ferrari concluded that as learning got more self-regulated across a student's academic career, procrastination ended up rising.

Research Questions

This study aimed to ascertain how academic procrastination is related to the academic performance of Grade-12 senior high school students of MSU-Sulu. Specifically, this explores the answers to the following queries:

1. What is the demographic profile of the grade 12 senior high school students in MSU-Sulu in terms of gender?
2. What is the level of academic performance of the students?
3. What is the level of academic procrastination of the students?
4. Is there a significant difference in the level of academic procrastination of the students when they are classified according to their gender?
5. Is academic procrastination associated with the academic performance of the students?

METHODOLOGY

Locale of the study

The study was conducted at MSU-Sulu. The researchers looked for students of 12th graders as their respondents and each respondent was given a survey questionnaire to be answered by them. The study was conducted in the second semester of the academic year 2023-2024.

Research Design

The researchers used a descriptive correlational research design to determine the relationship between academic procrastination and the academic performance of the respondents. Descriptive correlational design is used in research studies that aim to provide static pictures of situations as well as establish the relationship between different variables (McBurney & White 2009). It also investigated the influence of the demographic profile of the respondents on the relationship of academic procrastination on their academic performance. The research that was conducted was Quantitative research, a scientific method to gather numerical data.

Sampling Design

The sampling technique used in this particular study was purposive sampling, which means that the researcher purposively chose all the senior high school Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) and General Academic Strand (GAS) students of Mindanao State University- Sulu. One hundred twenty (120) students were optimized as subjects.

Research Instrument

The researchers used an adopted and modified Procrastination Assessment Scale-Student (PASS) as a research instrument. The PASS is a comprehensive measure of Academic procrastination. It assesses Five aspects including writing a term paper, studying for exams, keeping up with reading assignments, attendance tasks, and school activities in general. The Procrastination Assessment Scale-Student (PASS) was developed by Solomon & Rothblum (1984) to assess the prevalence of and reasons for academic procrastination. The PASS is the most widely used scale to explore procrastination on academically related tasks (Ferrari, Johnson, &McCown 1995) and has been shown to generate reliable and valid scores (Ferrari, 1989). However, there were few changes from the said instrument as it was said to be adopted and modified.

Statistical Treatment of Data

Descriptive analysis was performed to obtain the number of students whose academic performance is related to academic procrastination. The researchers used Four of descriptive statistical tools: Frequency and Percentage to answer research question number 1, Mean for research question numbers 2 and 3, T-test for the following research question number 4, and Correlation to answer research question number 5.

Scope and Delimitation

This study focuses on academic procrastination: and its relationship to the academic performance of grade-12 senior high school students. The respondent of this study is delimited to the Science Technology Engineering and Mathematics (STEM) and General Academic Strand (GAS) students of Mindanao State University- Sulu. during the school year 2023-2024.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1

Demographic Profile of the Students in terms of Gender

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	60	50.0
Female	60	50.0
Total	120	100.0

Table 1 shows the frequency and percentage distribution of values in terms of gender. As shown in the table, 60 or 60.0 of the respondents are male as well as female. This means that there is an equal distribution of the number of respondents for both males and females.

Table 2

Level of Student's Academic Performance

	Mean	Std. Deviation	Description
GPA	88.7	2.9	Very Satisfactory

Legend: Excellent = 90-100; Very Satisfactory = 85-89; Satisfactory = 80-84; Fairly Satisfactory = 75-79; Did not Meet the Expectation = 74 below

Table 2 shows the average grade of the students. The average grade of the students in the first semester is 88.7 which corresponds to the description very satisfactory. This means that the students of MSU- Sulu senior high school perform well on their academic performance.

Similar to the findings of Jhoselle Tus (2020) the level of academic performance of senior high school students was mostly satisfactory and very satisfactory.

Table 3

Level of Student's Academic Procrastination

Writing a term paper.	Mean	Std. deviation	Description
To what degree do you procrastinate on this task?	3.5	1.1	Nearly always procrastinate
To what degree is procrastination on	3.5	1.0	Nearly always procrastinate

this task a problem to you?			
To What extent do you want to decrease your tendency to procrastinate on this task?	3.8	1.0	Nearly always procrastinate
Studying for exams.			
To what degree do you procrastinate on this task?	4.0	1.0	Nearly always procrastinate
To what degree is procrastination on this task a problem to you?	3.8	1.0	Nearly always procrastinate
To What extent do you want to decrease your tendency to procrastinate on this task?	3.9	1.0	Nearly always procrastinate
Keeping up with reading assignments.			
To what degree do you procrastinate on this task?	3.8	1.1	Nearly always procrastinate
To what degree is procrastination on this task a problem to you?	3.6	0.9	Nearly always procrastinate
To What extent do you want to decrease your tendency to procrastinate on this task?	3.8	1.0	Nearly always procrastinate
Attendance task: Meeting with your adviser, making an appointment with your professor, etc.			
To what degree do you procrastinate on this task?	3.4	1.4	Nearly always procrastinate

To what degree is procrastination on this task a problem to you?	3.5	1.2	Nearly always procrastinate
To What extent do you want to decrease your tendency to procrastinate on this task?	3.5	1.9	Nearly always procrastinate
School activities in general.			
To what degree do you procrastinate on this task?	3.9	1.1	Nearly always procrastinate
To what degree is procrastination on this task a problem to you?	3.9	0.9	Nearly always procrastinate
To What extent do you want to decrease your tendency to procrastinate on this task?	4.0	1.0	Nearly always procrastinate
Total	3.7	1.1	Nearly always procrastinate

Legend: (4.20-5.00) Always procrastinate; (3.40-4.19) Nearly always procrastinate; (2.60-3.39) Sometimes procrastinate; (1.80-2.59) Almost never procrastinate; (1.00-1.79) Never procrastinate

Table 3 presents the level of academic procrastination of the students. The grand mean obtained 3.7 corresponds to the verbal description of nearly always. This means that there is academic procrastination on the part of the students.

Similar to the study of Solomon & Rothblum (1984) found that among American undergraduate college students, 27.6% reported that they nearly always procrastinate on studying for exams, 30.1% procrastinate on reading weakly assignments, and 46% procrastinate on writing papers. Also related to the study of Ozer et.al (2009) that with 784 undergraduate students in Turkey, 33% nearly always procrastinated when writing term papers. In a later study, Ozer (2011) found that with 150 undergraduate students in Turkey, 56% procrastinated when studying for exams, 39% procrastinated on completed reading assignments, and 38% procrastinated when writing term papers. Thus, the result suggested that among the different types of assignments, undergraduate students will procrastinate on different tasks. However, due to the limited number of studies examining academic procrastination based on tasks, no formal conclusions can be made presently.

Table 4*Gender difference in student's level of Academic Procrastination*

Gender	Male		Female		T	p-value
	M	SD	M	SD		
Variable	3.7	0.8	3.7	0.6	-.471	.639

*Significant at $p < 0.05$

Table 4 shows the significant difference in the level of academic procrastination as classified according to the respondent's gender. A T-test for independent sample was utilized to determine the difference in the level of academic procrastination of the students when they were classified according to their gender. The result shows that there is no significant difference in the level of academic procrastination between male (3.7) and female (3.7) respondents, $t(-.471)$, $p(-.639)$. The result shows that both genders have the same level of academic procrastination.

The finding of the study is related to the study of Solomon & Rothblum (1988) the result of self-reported procrastination data shows that there were no significant gender differences in any area of academic procrastination or total self-reported procrastination. It was also shown that both genders have higher levels of academic procrastination. Thus, it can be concluded that gender does not play a major role in determining the level of academic procrastination.

Table 5*Association of Academic Procrastination and Academic Performance*

Variables	Pearson Correlation	Sig. (2-tailed)
Academic Procrastination	-.257**	.005
Academic Performance	1	-

Note: $N=120$
 $p < .05$. ** $p < .01$

Table 5 shows the association between academic procrastination and academic performance. A Pearson Correlation was utilized to determine the association between academic procrastination and the academic performance of the students. The result shows that there is a low negative ($r = -.257^{**}$) significant ($p = .005$) relationship between the two variables. As variable x (academic procrastination) increases, variable y (academic performance) decreases. It means that the higher the level of the student's academic procrastination is, the lower their academic performance can be. Thus, academic procrastination is associated with the academic performance of the students.

several studies have found that academic procrastination is slightly related to academic performance (Beck et. al, 2000; Beswick et al., 1988; Lay 1986; Pychyl et al., 2000; Solomon & Rothblum 1988). It is assumed that people who procrastinate academically will have lower grades and lower academic achievement when compared to their non-procrastinating peers due to having poorer self-regulation skills (Zimmerman,

et. al., 1992). Due to the inconsistent result, further examination into this topic is greatly needed.

Conclusions

Based on the indicated findings, the following conclusions were drawn:

The level of academic performance of the students is very satisfactory. This can be concluded that the grade-12 senior high school students of MSU-Sulu are soaring high despite the given school activities and other circumstances that help improve their full potential. The level of academic procrastination of the students is nearly always. This means that there is academic procrastination on the part of the students. Students nearly always procrastinate in any academic-related activities which results in a high level of academic procrastination. The findings also revealed that gender does not play a major role in determining the significant difference in the level of academic procrastination. This is because both genders have the same level of academic procrastination. Lastly, the result of the association between academic procrastination and the academic performance of the students implies that both variables are associated. The higher the level of academic procrastination of the students, the lower their academic performance can be.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions presented, the following recommendations are suggested:

Organize your goal. One of the very ways to avoid academic procrastination is to get the goal organized. To be more organized, students need to clarify what needs to be done and when they can complete it. By being more focused and organized, thinking through this question will help them manage their time effectively.

Eliminate distractions. It is also recommended to put aside distractions. Distractions are time killers and are the primary way people procrastinate. Setting priorities serves the main purpose of putting distractions aside. Self-discipline is essential if students are to be able to concentrate on just one thing. Furthermore, by postponing pleasure for the moment and focusing more on finishing the more important chores, they might cultivate healthy study habits. In essence, students must constantly assess their progress in order to refine their methods and determine which tactics are most effective for them.

Remember the due dates. Students Being aware of their deadlines will assist them in developing positive planning habits. It will also assist them in preventing last-minute homework delays.

These recommendations are a big help to those Grade-12 senior high school students who want to reduce their procrastinating tendencies and be able to achieve more

in regards to their academic performance. It will also benefit the teachers as well as the parents as they help guide those students to avoid academic procrastination.

Furthermore, the researchers' study gives enlightenment to society and helps contribute knowledge in the field of research with regards to Academic Procrastination as well as help future researchers to look for information concerning Academic Procrastination and Academic Performance towards their future studies.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

In this study, the researchers observed the ethics protocol such as the privacy and confidentiality of the research respondents. The research procedure was conducted with rigorous adherence to plagiarism guidelines, ensuring that the results were interpreted impartially and that their usage was limited to legitimate research.

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